

***FACTORS INFLUENCING FINTECH ADOPTION
BEHAVIOR OF MILLENNIALS IN NEPAL: EVIDENCE
FROM KARNALI PROVINCE, NEPAL***

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Abstract

Purpose: *This study examines the factors influencing the intention of millennials in the Karnali Province of Nepal to adopt FinTech.*

Methods: *This study utilized a descriptive and causal-comparative research design. The target population was millennial respondents aged between 28 and 40 in the Karnali Province. The purposive sampling technique was employed to select 410 samples. Data were collected through structured questionnaires administered physically and online and then analyzed using structural equation modeling to estimate the relationships between observed variables and latent constructs.*

Findings/ Results: *This study uncovers that digital literacy, trust in technology, perceived ease of use, and social influence are the key determinants in fintech adoption behavior among millennials. These findings provide practical insights that can be used to design effective strategies for promoting FinTech adoption among this demographic.*

Conclusion: *The study concludes that by enhancing digital literacy, fostering trust in technological platforms, improving the user-friendliness of financial technology, and leveraging the power of social influence, we can potentially witness a significant increase in the adoption of FinTech solutions in Nepal, paving the way for a more digitally inclusive society.*

Keywords: **FinTech Adoption, Millennials, Digital Literacy, Karnali Province, Structural Equation Modeling**

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